

The three-dimensional signal collection field for fiber photometry in brain tissue

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RAW DATA

Download the file *Fluorescein.zip* for collection fields in quasi transparent fluorescent medium. Within the zip archive you'll find raw data (microscope and fiber acquired tiff stacks and results from ray-tracing simulations) and Matlab code for their processing, organized in different folders by fiber NA (0.22, 0.39, and 0.50) and sample number (A, B, C, and D).

Download the file *Brain.zip* for collection fields in fluorescently stained brain slice. Within the zip archive you'll find raw data (microscope and fiber acquired tiff images) and Matlab code for their processing, organized in different folders by fiber NA (0.39 and 0.50) and sample number (A, B, and C).

Download the file *PhotometryEfficiency.zip* for photometry efficiency in fluorescently stained brain slice. Within the zip archive you'll find raw data (non de-scanned microscope and fiber acquired tiff images and through de-scanned pinhole images) and Matlab code for their processing, organized in different folders by fiber NA (0.39 and 0.50).

ZEMAX MODEL

Download the file *Zemax.zip* for Zemax models for determining light collection fields in homogeneous and scattering medium. Within the zip archive you'll find the Zemax lens models (zmx files) and macros (zpl files), and a guidelines document.

MATLAB FUNCTIONS

Download the file *MatlabFunctions.zip* for the definition of Matlab functions required from the processing scripts.